

Funded by the
European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon-MSCA
Staff Exchange 2022 program under the grant agreement 1011361612.

Project: 1011361612 – SameMultiPhys –HORIZON-MSCA-2022-SE-01
Novel Biophysical Tools to Measure Multiple Parameters in The Same Cell

DELIVERABLE D4.2

REPORT OF THE RESULTS OF VERIFICATION USING CELL LINES

Due Date of Deliverable	M24	Completion Date of Deliverable	31/10/2025
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WP no.	WP4	WP Title	Testing and validating prototypes
Dissemination level	Public		

Start date of the project	01/11/2023	Duration	48 months
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Version	V1.0	Status	Final Version
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Version Log

Issue Date	Rev. No.	Author	Change

Coordinator:

Participants (3):

Partners (4):

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Introduction

1.1 Context within the SameMultiPhys project

The testing and validation of prototype microfluidic devices that can perform multiparameter, same-cell assays is of high interest for both fundamental biological research and the advancement of mechanobiology tools. Within this context, as part of Work Package 4 (WP4: Testing and Validating Prototypes, led by CNRS), this deliverable (D4.2) builds upon the initial design and fabrication efforts of the prototypes and focuses on their preliminary validation using cell-based assays. The goal is to assess the feasibility, functionality, and compatibility of the devices with living cells, providing a foundation for subsequent optimization and calibration. Specifically, the validation work described here uses two model cell systems, S180 murine sarcoma cells and ARPE-19 human retinal pigment epithelium cells, laying the groundwork for integration into more complex multi-parameter studies in future phases of WP4 (Start Month 13, End Month 47).

Although the tasks under WP4 encompass a broad range of prototype testing and validation, including flow characterization, feasibility studies, and calibration comparisons, this report focuses specifically on the initial validation of the prototype devices using cell-based assays, reflecting the current stage as of Month 24. Secondments at New York University (NYU) are currently ongoing, involving researchers from UPM, CNRS, TAU, and UNIFI, related to WP4; therefore, the experimental data from these secondments has not yet been included in this document. In addition, secondments at the University of Toronto (UT) have not yet been executed. These secondments are scheduled for Years 3–4 of the project, and consequently, the work related to the characterization of immune T cells and fluorescent nanotracers within cells will be addressed in subsequent deliverables.

This report (D4.2) thus provides a detailed account of the preliminary validation experiments performed on the prototype microfluidic devices using two model cell systems: S180 murine sarcoma cells and ARPE-19 human retinal pigment epithelium cells. S180 cells were used as a robust model to assess device feasibility and handling during the secondments at CNRS, while ARPE-19 cells were employed to test device performance under conditions closer to the intended physiological application with immune T cells. The results establish a baseline for device functionality and will inform further optimization, calibration, and multi-parameter validation in the subsequent phases of WP4.

1.2 Objectives of this deliverable

The main objective of this deliverable is to validate the performance of the microfabricated device for the simultaneous measurement of viscoelastic and electrical properties in individual cells, which has been developed and instrumentalized in the first part of the project. Specifically, this deliverable aims to:

- O.1. Verify the microfluidic devices' ability to capture reproducible mechanical and electrical responses from different cell lines, following the development of an automated system for analyzing these properties.

- O.2 Use model systems (S180 and ARPE-19 cells) to confirm the reliability of the platform and its suitability for biological samples relevant to immunological and disease studies, presenting preliminary data.
- O.3 Establish the methodological basis for subsequent verification with T cells and activated T cells, in order to assess the potential of the measured biophysical parameters as indicators of activation state and aging.

1.3 Scientific background

Cellular function and phenotype are closely linked to a cell's biophysical properties, such as deformability, viscoelasticity, and electrical impedance. Changes in these parameters accompany essential biological processes including activation, differentiation, and disease progression. Measuring these properties at the single-cell level provides valuable information for understanding mechanobiological mechanisms and identifying label-free biomarkers of cellular state [1–2].

Despite advances in single-cell technologies, most existing tools measure either mechanical or electrical characteristics independently, limiting the ability to correlate these parameters directly. The SameMultiPhys project addresses this challenge by developing an integrated microfluidic platform capable of simultaneous viscoelastic and electrical characterization of individual cells as they pass through micro-constrictions.

In this context, a polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS)-based microdevice incorporating platinum electrodes and constriction channels has been designed and fabricated in the first part of the project, as documented in previous deliverables. The system allows real-time impedance spectroscopy and deformation analysis of single cells flowing through microchannels. The present deliverable documents the verification of this device using S180 cells and ARPE-19 cells, providing experimental evidence that supports its use in subsequent biological assays focused on T-cells activation and aging.

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Materials and methods

2.1 Cell lines

2.2.1 S180 cells

S180, a murine sarcoma cell line, was cultured under standard conditions and maintained through regular passages to ensure healthy proliferation. Cells were counted using a Neubauer chamber and prepared for experiments in defined quantities. When in suspension, the diameter of the S180 cells is generally in the range of 15-20 μm (**Figure 1a**).

This cell line was used in the validation tests performed during the secondments at CNRS in Year 1-2 of the project.

2.2.2 ARPE-19 cells

ARPE-19, a commercial retinal pigment epithelium cell line, was cultured and maintained under standard conditions. Weekly cell passages were performed at 80% confluence, and cell counting was conducted using a Neubauer chamber. ARPE-19 cells typically have a diameter of 15-20 μm when in suspension (**Figure 1b**). Experiments included both live and fixed cells, the latter prepared according to the Miltenyi Biotec protocol. Approximately $4\text{--}5 \times 10^5$ cells were used per experiment, while the remainder sustained the cell line for ongoing studies.

This cell line was used in the validation tests performed during the secondments at UPM in Year 1-2 of the project.

Figure 1. Cell lines used in the validation experiments. (a) S180 cells. (b) ARPE-19 cells.

2.2 Microfabricated device

The platform used for the validation experiments consists of a 20 μm -high microfluidic channel embedded in a polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) mold bonded to a glass substrate with pre-defined platinum (Pt) electrodes contact pads (**Figure 2a-b**). A SU-8 mold was prepared for PDMS casting, forming constriction-based flow cytometry channels. The central part of this channel has a constriction of width of 5 μm (**Figure 2c-d**).

Figure 2. (a) Scheme of simultaneous viscoelastic and electrical characterization of cells. (b) Design of the microfluidic platform with constriction-based PDMS chips bonded to a glass substrate with Pt electrodes. (c-d). SEM images of the real mold used to fabricate PDMS chips.

2.3 Experimental setup

The experimental setup for performing cell assays using microfluidic devices requires a variety of instruments and materials, as shown in **Figure 3**.

First, an inverted biological microscope (Meiji Techno TC5400) equipped with a high-speed camera (Basler acA720-520um) was used, which is connected to a workstation to record the passage of cells through the constrictions of a channel. For single-constriction channels, a 40 \times objective is used; for channels with three constrictions, a 20 \times objective is employed; and for channels with 12 constrictions, a 10 \times objective is required. The Basler camera is controlled using the Pylon Viewer software, which allows, among other functions, recording and modifying camera settings. Its operation will be briefly described in subsequent sections.

To introduce cells into the device, 1 mL single-use Luer Lock syringes (M28 Changzhou Shuangma Medical Devices Co., Ltd., CE- and ISO 13485-certified) are used, connected to fine needles (Darwin Blunt-end Luer Lock Syringe Needles). The syringe is placed in a syringe pump (Fisherbrand™ KDS100 Legacy) operating at a constant flow rate, expressed in mL/h. On the other end, the fluid exiting the system through the outlet tubing is collected in a beaker for subsequent disposal. Both the beaker and the pump are positioned at an appropriate height using, for

example, lifting platforms, so that the syringe pump is elevated relative to the microscope and the microscope stand is above the beaker.

To connect the syringe to the inlet cavity of the microfluidic device and the outlet to the beaker, segments of tubing (Masterflex® Transfer Tubing PTFE MFLX06417-21 - VWR) are cut with a scalpel at an angle that facilitates insertion into the device cavities. In this way, the system is fully sealed.

Before experiments, channels are inspected for defects, background images are captured, and tubing connections are prepared using cell culture medium to ensure smooth flow. Cells are loaded into a syringe mounted in a pump, and baseline images of the channel are taken before initiating flow (typically 0.1–1 mL/h). During acquisition, individual trials are recorded when cells pass through the constrictions, with relevant observations noted for later analysis.

Figure 3. Overview of the experimental setup for the mechanical characterization experiments. The following components can be observed: (1) the microscope, (2) the modular platform, (3) the syringe pump, (4) the camera connected to the workstation, and (5) the beaker.

2.4 Device instrumentation and data acquisition

The experimental setup for microfluidic cell assays combines imaging, fluid control, and simultaneous electrical measurements. An inverted microscope with a high-speed camera (Basler acA720-520um) records cells passing through channel constrictions at 100 Hz, while images are stored in a structured directory system. For experiments involving simultaneous impedance measurements, microfluidic devices with integrated electrodes are connected to an oscilloscope with an impedance analyzer (**Figure 4**). Acquisition parameters are set via WaveForms, and a Python script synchronizes impedance data with imaging in Pylon Viewer. Data, including impedance magnitude and phase, are exported to CSV files for each trial. After experiments, devices and the workspace are cleaned with 70% ethanol, and disposable materials are safely discarded.

Figure 4. Microfluidic system for viscoelastic and electrical characterization of cells. The PDMS chip with microconstrictions is bonded to a glass slide and the Pt electric contact pads are connected via cables to an impedance analyzer (Digilent Analog Discovery 2). Electrical impedance measurements were recorded at three frequencies (1000, 2236Hz and 5000 Hz). The PDMS chip includes an inlet and outlet for injecting cells under a controlled flow rate using a syringe pump or a pressure controller.

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Results and discussion

3.1 Automatic analysis of viscoelastic and electrical properties

This section presents the methodology and results of the automated analysis routine developed to extract mechanical and electrical properties of cells passing through microfluidic constrictions. The workflow integrates image processing, electrical measurements, and computational modelling in a unified MATLAB framework.

3.1.1 Image processing and mechanical analysis

The analysis routine is implemented in an object-oriented MATLAB architecture comprising four main classes:

1. **Device:** Represents the microfluidic device, storing ID, image paths, constriction geometry, flow rate (Q), sampling frequency (f_s), and objects for Channels and ElectricData.
2. **Channel:** Represents one constriction; stores image coordinates for the region of interest, channel geometry (width W_{ch} , entry radius ρ , wall angle α), reference line for cell movement, and an array of Event objects.
3. **Event:** Refers to frames where a cell passes the constriction; processes mechanical (E_0 , g_∞ , τ_R) and electrical properties (C_2 , R_2 , R_3), along with cell displacement (A_L).
4. **ElectricData:** Represents electrical measurements (impedance magnitude, phase, frequencies) and baseline constriction data (C_1 , R_1).

Three types of images are processed test images (captured during experiments), base images (pre-experiment images for channel geometry), and background images (to correct optical artifacts). These images were analyzed automatically, as described below, to fit the quasi-linear viscoelastic (QLV) model [3] and to estimate key mechanical parameters, including the instantaneous elastic modulus (E_0), the stress relaxation parameter (g_∞), and the relaxation time (τ_c) (**Figure 5a**).

Experimental image data were loaded into the workspace via the Device object, which stored the file paths due to the large dataset size. Users selected directories containing base and background images, and electrical measurements were synchronized using the epoch time of experiment start, which differed between CTB-UPM and CNRS-France. For each constriction, the images were processed to enhance low-contrast structures, remove artifacts, and correct illumination inhomogeneities. Channel edges were detected, and the region of interest was defined. The upper edge profile was smoothed and differentiated to identify key points, including the start, midpoint, and end of the constriction. Images were cropped to standard dimensions, and geometric parameters such as entry radius and wall angle were set based on ideal designs. A blockage vector tracked obstructions in each frame.

Cell passages through the constriction were identified by comparing intensity profiles between base and experimental images. Frames showing significant differences were marked as blocked, and events were recorded with their start and end frames. Cell segmentation was performed using a modified convolutional neural network trained on 198 images of varying constriction sizes. The first frames of each event were analysed to confirm the

presence of a cell and estimate its initial radius, while subsequent frames were used to track the front and rear positions of the cell. Quadratic fitting identified maximum curvature points, and the cell radius was estimated by interpolating against theoretical curves provided by collaborators. Final mechanical vectors, including normalized cell advance (A_L/W_{ch}), were then computed.

Figure 5. Representative image of a S180 cell undergoing aspiration with key parameters automatically quantified using an AI-enhanced custom MATLAB script. The time-dependent curve of normalized aspirated length (A_L/W_{ch}) can be fitted using the quasi-linear viscoelastic (QLV) model to estimate the instantaneous elastic modulus elastic modulus (E_0), the stress relaxation parameter (g_∞), and the relaxation time (τ_c).

3.1.2 Electrical measurements

The electrical behaviour of the system was described using an equivalent circuit model. In this model, C_1 , R_2 and R_3 represent the capacitance and resistance of the medium and electrodes, while C_2 and R_2 corresponded to the cell membrane capacitance and cytoplasm resistance. Any additional capacitance from the electrodes was found to be negligible, on the order of less than a picofarad ($< \text{pF}$).

Data acquisition was automated using a set of Python scripts that synchronized image capture with electrical measurements. Once acquired, the electrical data were imported into MATLAB as **ElectricData** objects. Timestamps from the electrical recordings were aligned with the corresponding image acquisition times. To extract circuit parameters, the Levenberg-Marquardt nonlinear least-squares fitting method was applied. Baseline values of C_1 and R_1 were determined from periods when no cell was present in the constriction. During cell events, the parameters C_2 , R_2 , and R_3 were estimated. Events were classified to differentiate baseline periods from those containing a cell, and the electrical properties were temporally aligned with the mechanical measurements, such as normalized cell advance (A_L/W_{ch}), allowing for a synchronized analysis of the cell's mechanical and electrical behaviour.

3.2 Experimental validation using S180 cells

As shown in **Figure 6a**, the experimental validation was performed using S180 cells in a constriction-based microfluidic device mounted on an inverted microscope. Individual cells were observed as they deformed while passing through the constriction, and their contours were automatically segmented over time (**Figure 6b**). This time-resolved segmentation allowed the quantitative tracking of cell deformation, providing the basis for mechanical analysis. For each cell, the normalized aspirated length (A_L/W_{ch}) was measured as a function of time and fitted to the quasi-linear viscoelastic (QLV) model [3] (**Figure 6c**). From this fitting, key viscoelastic parameters, the

instantaneous elastic modulus (E_0), the stress relaxation parameter (g_∞), and the relaxation time (τ_c) were extracted for 10 cells (**Figure 6e**), capturing the mechanical response of each S180 cell under confinement.

Figure 6. (a). Experimental setup in an inverted microscope. (b). S180 cell deforming in a constriction-based microfluidic device. The automatic segmentation of the cell is shown below as a function of time. (c). Normalized aspirated length (A_L/W_{ch}) as a function of time and fitting of the QLV model of a given S180 cell, yielding viscoelastic parameters. (d). Electrical and viscoelastic parameters of $n=10$ cells S180 as function of the normalized cell radius (R_c/W_{ch}).

In parallel, the electrical response of each cell was recorded and analysed, yielding estimates of relevant electrical parameters during deformation: $R_2 = 0.6$ MO, $C_2 = 36$ nF. By combining mechanical and electrical measurements, the relationship between cell viscoelasticity and electrical properties could be examined. Across a sample of ten S180 cells, both electrical and viscoelastic parameters were analysed as a function of the normalized cell radius (R_c/W_{ch}), demonstrating the reproducibility of the experimental approach and providing insight into how cell size influences its mechanical and electrical behaviour.

3.3 Experimental validation using ARPE-19 cells

ARPE-19 cells were observed as they deformed while passing through the constriction, and their contours were automatically segmented over time (**Figure 7**). As with S180 cells, this time-resolved segmentation allowed the quantitative tracking of cell deformation, providing the basis for mechanical analysis. For each cell, the normalized aspirated length (A_L/W_{ch}) was measured as a function of time and fitted to the QLV model [3]. From this fitting, key viscoelastic parameters, the instantaneous elastic modulus (E_0), the stress relaxation parameter (g_∞), and the relaxation time (τ_c), capturing the mechanical response of each ARPE-19 cell. The analysis of the 10 events shows that the average estimated $E_0 = 6220 \pm 1540$ Pa. The mean long-term modulus is $g_\infty = 0.674 \pm 0.120$, while the average relaxation time τ is 0.393 ± 0.030 s. The mean cell membrane capacitance is $C_2 = (3.41 \pm 0.02) \cdot 10^{-8}$ F, showing good consistency among the measurements. The cytoplasm resistance exhibits a mean value of $R_2 = (2.0 \pm 0.4) \cdot 10^5 \Omega$.

Figure 7. The automatic segmentation of an ARPE-19 cell passing through the constriction.

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Conclusions and future work

This deliverable had three main objectives: first, to verify the device's capability to capture reproducible mechanical and electrical responses across different cell lines; second, to validate the reliability of the platform and its suitability for biological samples using model systems such as S180 and ARPE-19 cells; and third, to establish the methodological foundation for future experiments with T cells, aimed at evaluating the potential of the measured biophysical parameters as indicators of activation state and cellular aging.

The methodology for simultaneous measurements was successfully validated, accurately recording both electrical signals and images, while automatically detecting the passage of cells through the microfluidic devices. The programmed scripts ensured precise synchronization between electrical measurements and image acquisition. Additionally, the equivalent circuit model developed to represent cell behavior produced coherent results, although further data collection is required to complete the characterization and compare it with previously reported literature.

A custom analysis code was implemented to automate data processing that was previously performed manually, allowing for faster and unbiased analysis. Its performance was tested at multiple stages, and the cell segmentation algorithm accurately tracked the advance of the cell front in 80% or more of cases.

Multiple experiments were carried out both to validate the code and to characterize preliminary results of mechanical and electrical properties of S180 and ARPE-19 cells were obtained. Building on this work, future studies will extend the characterization to T cells and explore the relationship between mechanical and electrical parameters in biologically relevant contexts.

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